

Aloidendron dichotomum Quiver Tree

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Monocot

Size: 7-9 m.

Distribution:

The quiver tree is a conspicuous component of the arid regions known as Namaqualand and Bushmanland. It occurs in rocky areas from near Nieuwoudtville northwards into Namibia and eastwards to Upington and Kenhardt.

Importance:

The quiver tree, a well-known South African and Namibian aloe, is valued for traditional San uses and hollow trunks. It is listed under CITES II and occurs in several protected areas. Climate change may contribute to population decline. Research on growth, mortality, germination, stress tolerance, seed dispersal, pollinators, genetics, and herbivory remains vital for its long-term survival.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 307.19 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.98 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 11.84 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.6% [Single: 91.1%, Duplicated: 7.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 614.44 kilobases

Contig number: 16 685

Sample Contributor contact details:

Mr Thabang Makola

South African National Biodiversity Institute

T.makola@sanbi.org.za

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